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Development of Leadership Qualities of the Managerial Staff as a Factor Influencing the Resilience of the University Library in the Crisis

Objective. The purpose of the publication is to determine the role of leadership development of the managerial staff in ensuring the management of the university library in the dynamic crisis conditions of long-term martial law. The article analyses the features of resilient organisations that promptly restore controllability and perform work tasks. The leadership qualities, the development of which is expedient in the team in the conditions of crisis changes, are considered. **Methods.** The conducted analysis covered the scientific publications on the topic of the study. The study used empirical methods to determine the effectiveness of leadership development among library managers. **Results.** The influence of the state of technical and social components on the resilience of the organisation is considered. Technical components are difficult to influence by the library administration, unlike social ones. That is why the main focus is on the regulation of social components. Based on the practical results of the library's work, the expediency of forming a leadership style to ensure the library's resilience in crisis conditions is substantiated. **Conclusions.** Thus, we believe that in crisis conditions, the resilience of an organisation can be enhanced by developing the leadership skills of the library management. During the period of uncertain crisis conditions of martial law, these leadership styles normalise the psychological climate in the team and set employees up for results.

Keywords: management; academic libraries; organisational resilience; ethical leadership; democratic leadership; transformational leadership; shared leadership

Introduction

Since February 2022, the armed aggression of the Russian Federation has been ongoing in Ukraine. This is accompanied by the presence of long-term critical circumstances caused by hostilities. When organising the work of higher education institutions in Ukraine amid the crisis, the creation of the following necessary conditions is taken into account: the implementation of the security component and ensuring the quality of the educational and scientific process. The challenges faced by institutions in the current circumstances can be successfully addressed only by resilient organisations that maintain control in dynamic conditions of uncertainty.

The resilience of libraries ensures that they fulfil their important social mission of providing scientific and information support for the development of society and preserving Ukraine's documentary heritage on the path to enhancing equity, diversity, accessibility and inclusion. Resilient organisations play a crucial role in the development of resilient communities (Krsmanovic et al., 2024).

“Organisational resilience is the ability of state authorities, local governments, enterprises, institutions, organisations to identify, prepare for, respond to threats, adapt to changes in the security environment, and maintain sustainable functioning before, during and after a crisis situation in order to maintain functioning and further development” (Pro rishennia Rady natsionalnoi bezpeky i oborony Ukrainy, 2021). Organisational resilience is the ability of an organisation to overcome a shock and return to a state of productivity through flexibility (adaptation). Ukrainian educational institutions operate in circumstances such as war, missile threats, power outages, fires, etc. This radically disrupts daily work for an indefinite period of time.

It is important for the academic library to maintain stability, manageability and find ways to continue to play the role of an information centre, actively integrate into as many internal and external processes of the university as possible. The continuous high-quality work of this unit is critical for the successful fulfilment of the tasks of the educational and scientific process. Unpredictable dynamic changes require constant monitoring by the library management, prompt planning of adaptive changes to management approaches at different time intervals, and development of methodological solutions that will ensure flexibility and efficiency of the management process.

Organisational agility is based on four processes: anticipation, monitoring, response and learning. *Anticipation* is the approach of decision makers to anticipate challenges to the system. *Monitoring* consists of observing and studying the functioning of the system to gain a clear understanding of its current state. *Response* is a set of actions and reactions aimed at performing and improving work processes. *Learning* involves the accumulation, study of experience and integration of knowledge for implementation in practice. The crisis has demonstrated the importance of developing organisational resilience for adaptation, rethinking and finding new opportunities (Krsmanovic et al., 2024).

According to S. Ducheck's conceptual model, a resilient organisation goes through three stages: expectation, coping and adaptation. *Expectation* refers to the period before a critical situation occurs and includes the key concepts of preparation, observation and identification. *The coping stage* takes place during a crisis. It requires analysing the situation and developing resilience strategies and mobilising the necessary resources to implement solutions. Management and coordination are complex processes that require leadership to act and develop overall plans. *The adaptation stage* represents the post-crisis period, when organisations reflect on successes and failures, draw conclusions, and implement long-term changes. At all stages of the crisis, effectiveness is ensured by an unprecedented level of interaction and cooperation within the organisation. It is also important to focus on the use and development of leadership qualities of managers at all levels when going through expectations, coping and adaptation (Duchek, 2020a; Duchek, Raetze, & Scheuch, 2020b). Research findings indicate that leadership is essential for increasing team effectiveness, quality of team experience, and team vitality (Tran & Vu, 2021).

Leadership development requires a willingness to reflect on what a leader is and what he or she wants to be. Leadership style is formed as a result of analysing the meaning of one's experience and defining one's own values, needs and expectations. Leadership determines the behaviour of a person characterised by high self-awareness, a strong internal moral position, the ability to perceive and analyse information in a balanced way and transparency of relations with subordinates. A predictive relationship between managerial leadership and the degree of engagement of institutional employees has been identified (McAuliffe, Bostain, & Witchel, 2019).

By engagement, we mean the physical and emotional state under the influence of which employees strive to do their job as well as possible (Lysytsia & Voitovych, 2017). Employees' sense of self-worth and usefulness, lack of fear of consequences for mistakes, and availability of resources necessary to fully perform their tasks lead to increased job engagement, which in turn leads to increased productivity (McAuliffe, Bostain, & Witchel, 2019). A well-established communication process within the organisation and a positive psychological climate in the team facilitate engagement. Therefore, managerial leadership requires an understanding of communication, motivation and relationship skills, which can be more effectively achieved by combining the qualities of collaborative, democratic and transformational and ethical leadership styles (Wilson, 2020).

The multiplicity of leadership styles and the use of the qualities inherent in these styles depend on the problem and is directly related to the level of communication skills possessed by

the leader. It is also known that the success of a style depends not only on its advantages, but also on the time when this style is used (Drivas, Sakas, & Giannakopoulos, 2016).

Democratic leadership is based on interacting with subordinates on an equal footing. This flattens the organisational hierarchy and allows employees to freely express their opinions and participate in management decisions. Democratic leadership focuses on effective communication and collaboration (Wilson, 2020). *Shared leadership* is based on communication, flexibility, and trust. As librarians are lifelong learners, their ability to take on management roles and make decisions without formal authority has made the concept of shared leadership possible (Wilson, 2020). Each team member brings knowledge, skills, and perspectives that contribute to the overall success of the team and the organisation, and the members recognise that no one can have all the information they need to make informed decisions (Krier, 2022). *Transformational leadership* is based on personal charisma, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration of the needs of employees, and aims to develop each person to their highest level of potential. The transformational approach is the most researched style for use in librarianship (Wilson, 2020). *Ethical leadership* is characterised by ethical behaviour and good interpersonal relationships, instilling the skills of such behaviour in employees. Ethical leaders demonstrate objectivity and impartiality, ethical behaviour, take into account the wishes of people and properly protect the rights of their employees. Ethical leadership is also an important factor in the development of an ethical organisational culture (Albdareen, Al-Gharaibeh, Alraqqad, & Maswadeh, 2024).

Communication is a fundamental skill for successful leadership, making people feel valued. Democratic, shared, transformational, and ethical leadership rely heavily on communication and relationships. While communication is crucial to providing support and building relationships, there are many other elements that are important to fostering high quality working relationships. A leader should understand not only the methods and goals of communication, but also the specifics of the relationship they have with their subordinates (Wilson, 2020). This will allow analysing and adjusting some communication processes.

Important areas inherent in the above leadership styles:

- Participation of team members in decision-making and involvement of employees in setting organisational goals. This promotes employee engagement and allows the manager to make the most of their experience (Wilson, 2020);
- Encouraging employees to generate innovative and creative solutions to problems. Encouraging critical thinking to seek diverse perspectives (Martin, 2016);
- Striving to develop a shared vision of problems and objectives by the team, and identifying strategies and actions that will help the library achieve this vision (Krier, 2022);
- Focus on developing leaders throughout the organisation so that each employee would feel empowered to take the initiative and do what is needed to fix a problem or initiate positive change (Martin, 2016);
- Building relationships with staff, tailored to meet the goals of library management;
- Frequent and open communication to provide quality feedback and celebrate achievements. Creating an environment that fosters active communication (Drivas, Sakas, & Giannakopoulos, 2016);
- Equal treatment of all employees, regardless of their level in the organisational hierarchy. Respect for employees promotes their engagement and maximises the use of their expertise;
- Developing active listening skills, which involves paying attention not only to the content of messages, but also to the feelings of employees. This depends on the emotional

intelligence of the manager, the ability to recognise verbal and non-verbal cues, and the ability to provide adequate feedback to the interlocutor. This aspect is not possible in online communication;

- Creating an atmosphere of trust, openness and sincerity in accordance with ethical standards (Albdareen, Al-Gharaibeh, Alraqqad, & Maswadeh, 2024);
- Willingness to learn from each other and recognise that one person cannot be competent in all matters (Cota, 2024).

The development of the above leadership styles contributes to the emergence of five key qualities that can help library leaders respond effectively to the crisis: resourcefulness, flexibility, presence, responsiveness and communication (Wakeling, et al., 2023).

Objective. The purpose of the publication is to determine the role of leadership development of the managerial staff in ensuring the management of the university library in the dynamic crisis conditions of long-term martial law. The article analyses the features of resilient organisations that promptly restore controllability and perform work tasks. Firstly, the influence of the state of technical and social components on the stability of the organisation is determined, with the main emphasis on the regulation of social components. Secondly, the article studies leadership qualities, the development of which is advisable in a team in the context of crisis changes, as such that will help management to normalise the psychological climate in the team, promote the involvement of employees and set them up for productive work. The conclusions are based on the practical results of the library's work.

Methods

The publications in the information-analytical systems Scopus and Web of Science are analysed in relation to the best world practices and the latest research on approaches to organising the work of an institution in the crisis conditions.

Based on the scientific publications, the concepts of “Organisational resilience”, “Employee’s involvement”, “Ethical leadership”, “Democratic leadership”, “Transformational leadership”, “Shared leadership” are analysed. The article identifies the processes on which the flexibility of an organisation is based. It considers the stages that a resilient organisation goes through in the face of rapid change. The study covers the composition of technical and social components of organisations. The identified elements and qualities make up the ethical, democratic, transformational and shared leadership styles.

The study used empirical methods to test the effectiveness of the approach. The reliability of the results is confirmed by the results of the library's work in 2023, some of which are described in the Results and Discussion section.

Results and Discussion

The task of maintaining control of a university library in a dynamic environment of uncertainty is a complex task, in which management needs to take into account a number of factors that apply to each employee and the unit as a whole.

A library, like other organisations, is a complex system that includes interrelated social and technical components. *Social components* include missions and goals, staff, and organisational culture. *Technical components* include work processes and practices, technology, as well as buildings and infrastructure. Any change in one of these components affects the others. The ability of a team to use its resources efficiently and demonstrate appropriate behaviour is a fundamental aspect of organisational resilience (Krsmanovic et al., 2024).

The social and technical components of the library should be considered in the context of the current crisis conditions that are currently in place and continue to change dynamically. It should be borne in mind that even in the absence of a crisis, a library is an organisation where technologies, methodology, and funding levels are constantly changing. The rapidity of these changes is a constant challenge that library management must cope with (Wilson, 2020).

Dynamic conditions are understood as rapid changes in internal and external factors that directly affect the organisation of the institution. Since the beginning of martial law, as of August 2024, the library of NTU “KhPI” has gone through two adaptation periods, during which the unit's management was not lost and its work continued.

The first period took place during the first half of martial law. The difficulty of this period for the library management was the organisation and resumption of the unit's main functions in the conditions of full remote work, technical and technological limitations. The application of the concept of developing shared leadership in the team has proved to be effective in simplifying the process of managing the university library in the crisis conditions while organising effective remote work of virtual teams (Odnovolykova & Hlavcheva, 2023).

The second adaptation period began in the spring of 2024 and was driven by the need to return to offline operation. It is currently ongoing. The authors have expressed their opinion on its complexity in the past: “An important issue that cannot be ignored when working remotely is planning to return to offline mode after the security situation is normalised. After all, there are many organisational changes taking place: service information is moving online, communication rules are changing significantly, etc. This implies separate preparation for the restoration of the offline mode according to other work algorithms” (Odnovolykova & Hlavcheva, 2023). It should be noted that the return to offline operation took place before the security situation was normalised.

In April 2024, a number of circumstances radically changed the working hours of the library staff. One of the critical factors changed. The library staff returned to work at their workplaces directly in the premises of the scientific and technical library on the university campus.

A comparative table of changes in the factors of influence on the current and last year's situation according to the proposed classification (Odnovolykova & Hlavcheva, 2023) is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Comparative table of changes in the factors of influence on the current and last year's situation

	2022-2023	2024
	Non-critical factors that do not require significant changes in the mode and organisation of processes and management to maintain operations	
1.	The need to ensure favourable working conditions	actual
2.	Globalisation and development of international cooperation	actual
3.	Measures to promote the organisation's competitiveness	actual
	Critical factors encourage the management to implement urgent unconditional changes in the mode of operation and to quickly find new approaches to managing processes in the organisation	
4.	Ensuring safety of staff and users	actual
5.	Unavailability of workplaces	Available jobs
6.	Martial law and the threat of armed aggression	actual
7.	The need to adapt work processes to changed conditions	actual

Access to workplaces for staff is a positive change in itself. Virtual communication has been replaced by real communication. The following problems have lost their relevance:

geographical dispersion of employees, heterogeneity of working conditions, incompatibility of hardware and software, time differences and inaccessibility of information resources for work.

Virtual teams that worked effectively in remote working conditions have lost their effectiveness in the restored offline mode, as the specifics of communication have changed. The virtual teams, which are not limited by the location of their members and communicate online, have been replaced by work in departments and specialisation of work areas according to the functions of the departments. The dynamics of indicators and the content of work have changed, as the list of work performed offline has been restored and the speed of creating own information resources has slowed down significantly (April 2024 – 40% fewer records created).

The library management is gradually implementing a number of measures aimed at adapting work processes to work in an offline format. This takes into account the asynchronous format of the educational process, and accordingly, remote services for teachers and students are maintained.

The critical factors (Table 1) have not lost their relevance, and employees are still experiencing the following: prolonged air raids with the need to stay in shelter for significant periods of time; power outages; and temporary stops of public transport. Librarians do not feel safe at their workplaces and are often in a state of high anxiety. In the online environment, everyone was responsible for their own safety, which gave them confidence, but now the administration's priority is to ensure the safety of staff and users in the face of increased potential and real danger at workplaces in the library building. To maintain a normal moral and psychological state, the staff needs support. The psychological stability of each employee will contribute to the stability of the team as a whole.

In order to maintain organisational resilience of the library while adapting to new conditions, it is necessary to take into account both social and technical components. The technical components depend on logistics, funding, internal policies of the organisation, etc. and are therefore difficult to influence and adapt. The minimal technical support has been implemented to enable the performance of tasks using information and communication technologies: automated workstations have been set up and software applications that have not been used for about 2 years have been updated.

The social components are based on work with personnel, so influence on them is possible and accessible to unit managers. The development of leadership skills in middle managers can have a positive impact on the behaviour of employees and set them up for rational behaviour in the face of danger, help them learn and use self-help and self-regulation mechanisms in case of anxiety.

It should be noted that the crisis has made the importance of physical safety and mental health of staff a priority (Krsmanovic et al., 2024).

The article focuses on the social components of the library as those that are subject to certain influence from the library management, ensure a healthy moral and psychological state of all employees, contribute to the resilience of the institution, and inspire the quality of work tasks.

Valuing employees, openness to cooperation, ability to make quick and correct decisions, caution and prudence, as well as strong personal traits (foresight, intuition, analytical thinking, empathy) are essential for crisis management (Aksay & Şendoğdu, 2022).

In times of crisis, staff are in a depressed moral and psychological state and experience emotional exhaustion. Management can help boost employee morale by providing job security, support, respect, encouragement for professional development, autonomy, valuing the personal contribution and skills of each employee, and listening to ideas that are put forward (Glusker, Emmelhainz, Estrada, & Dyess, 2022).

Due to prolonged anxiety and tension, there are cases of professional burnout of library

staff, which is an extreme condition caused by chronic stress. Morale is directly related to the employee's faith in the organisation in difficult crisis conditions. Technical limitations on the campus, lack of resources due to the institution's financial problems negatively affect the process of adaptation of employees to the "new normal" in the physical library space. Librarians' sense of insecurity in the workplace prompted some to decide to leave the profession. The level of library staffing is one of the main factors affecting morale in the workplace, as those who remain are forced to take on additional responsibilities and, consequently, a significant increase in workload. Library administrators should pay attention to the feelings of stress, anxiety, and overwork among staff. Many feel frustrated with their institution due to factors beyond their control (e.g. budgets, lack of a remote work policy). Staff should be made aware of opportunities to redistribute workloads and encouraged to maintain a healthy work-life balance (Berg, Salvesen, Barrett, & Lafazan, 2022).

Managers need to be aware that stress is common in environments characterised by inadequate resources, loss or anticipated loss of resources, and uncertain job role expectations. Library leadership has an impact on organisational culture, behaviour and staff health. Accordingly, developing leadership skills that will contribute to a better understanding of the level of staff burnout will help to develop strategies to mitigate existing burnout and develop a plan of appropriate preventive measures that will significantly reduce the burnout symptoms (Wood, Guimaraes, Holm, Hayes, & Brooks, 2020).

It should be noted that the leadership skills needed to train, support, and motivate staff ensure the continuity of service delivery and fulfilment of library and university objectives in the long run (Bynoe, 2022).

Management is a hard, continuous job on a daily basis. There is an unprecedented situation when the social crisis came unexpectedly, acutely and for a long time. Libraries did not have ready-made plans on how to ensure their performance and provide quality library services. In such a situation, managers must align their own expectations of their role with the changing needs and responsibilities of those they lead, and develop a leadership style that will help them motivate their staff, navigate change, and continue to perform their tasks in a way that avoids their exhaustion. Communication skills are now more important than ever for successful management. Mental health awareness has come to the fore during the crisis. Managers need to be aware of the stressors and mental health of the people they manage. Many are traumatised by the circumstances. If this reality is ignored, then staff turnover will continue and those who are working will show a decline in productivity. It also makes sense to show empathy and acknowledge the traumatic impacts not only on your employees, but also on your own life. The only way to broaden your own way of thinking and perception is to learn about people who have different experiences and what they are going through. It is important to let employees know that they can and should ask for help if needed, to make sure they do not take on more work than they can handle, and that work is distributed in a way that avoids burnout. For example, simply talking to staff about how they are doing demonstrates an important level of caring. An academic library director cannot change university policy, but they can make the library experience more comfortable for their staff through this approach, and sometimes this is crucial (Bynoe, 2022).

Most research studies have shown that continuing professional development is the best way to develop library leadership skills. However, some studies have shown that leadership experience, peer-to-peer learning, competitive environments, self-development, and career mobility were the most preferred ways to develop library leadership skills. Mentoring was also found to be another important strategy for developing library leadership skills.

Many studies emphasise that successful library leaders need to possess certain qualities as well as a certain set of skills that could help them overcome challenges: effective communication

skills, social skills and collaborative skills, which allows them to develop positive relationships with all library stakeholders, build a democratic culture of engagement in the library (Ashiq, Rehman, Safdar, & Ali, 2021).

The library administration cooperates with the unit's trade union to identify and better understand the immediate needs of employees and to support a democratic culture. A number of online and offline events were held to support the general psychological state of the staff and teach them methods and skills to overcome stress. At the invitation of the library administration, they were attended by specialists from the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of Social Systems Management named after Academician I. A. Ziaziun of NTU “KhPI”, practicing psychologists from the international non-governmental organisation Polish Humanitarian Action. In addition to general activities, employees take open distance learning courses on their own to maintain their own psychological health. Such measures help to stabilise the moral and psychological state of employees, contribute to the resilience of the team as a whole, and the library management can effectively create a working atmosphere for successful task solving merely by paying attention to the moral and psychological state of the staff.

At the same time, we consider it expedient to focus the attention of the management team at all levels on the development of individual leadership qualities, as leadership is developed and improved through education, training and mentoring at all levels of the organisation. NTU “KhPI” annually holds a school-seminar “Modern Pedagogical Technologies in Education”, which addresses many topical issues in education. In 2024, within the framework of the XXI International School-Seminar “Modern Pedagogical Technologies in Education” of NTU “KhPI”, 12 master classes were held, including the following ones dedicated to leadership development: “Efficiency of leadership qualities in extreme conditions”, “Influence of leadership development on traumatic experience of a person”, “Transformational leadership of a manager and a teacher: aiming for success”, etc. Every year, the library management has the opportunity to participate in these events to understand and develop their own leadership skills and competencies.

In addition to the traditional events that have already proved their effectiveness, it is planned to organise a number of in-library events with the involvement of specialists from the university departments that study management, leadership, and psychology: “Pedagogy and Psychology of Management of Social Systems named after Academician I. A. Ziaziun”, “Sociology and Public Administration”, “Management”.

In 2023, the library staff received an external high evaluation of the library's work from the Central Evaluation and Accreditation Agency ZEvA (Germany): “The highly motivated library staff made a lasting impression in their mission to provide users with the necessary publications.”

In 2023, the main focus was on fulfilling the practical, relevant tasks of the University through the use of available tools and technologies. In 2023, for the first time in the history of the library, we had record-breaking results: the indicators of the formation of the electronic catalogue and electronic repository of the scientific and technical library, as well as the activities related to the work of the information and resource centre “Without Barriers” and the Publication Support Centre increased significantly.

As of August 2024, the adaptation of work processes to the new conditions, which are still characterised by dynamism, uncertainty, and danger, is ongoing.

Conclusions

Thus, we believe that the emphasis on the development of leadership qualities of the management team in the dynamic crisis conditions of long-term martial law contributes to the resilience of the institution and has a positive impact on the management of the university library,

which is confirmed by the results of the work. It should be noted that under the above conditions, the library is undergoing professional evolutionary changes (changes in services, ways of providing content, approaches to the use of library space), which are also taken into account in the management of the library.

In the scientific and technical library of NTU “KhPI”, among the leadership qualities of the management team, there is a development and combination of the qualities of shared, democratic, transformational and ethical leadership styles. Based on practical experience, we can note that under different circumstances, one or another leadership style, or even a combination of some of their elements, can be effective.

Based on the results of empirical research, we can recommend that managers who want to develop their leadership skills to promote resilience and increase the effectiveness of communication with subordinates and improve their performance: focus on self-development, forming their own unique leadership style that best suits the current situation and tasks; apply techniques to avoid burnout; pay attention to the expectations and requests of subordinates and communicate more actively with them; develop active listening skills; foster an atmosphere of trust and mutual respect between all members of the unit.

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Розвиток лідерських якостей керівного складу як чинник впливу на стійкість бібліотеки університету в умовах кризи

Мета. Метою публікації є визначення ролі розвитку лідерства управлінського персоналу в забезпеченні управління університетською бібліотекою в динамічних кризових умовах тривалого воєнного стану. У статті проаналізовано особливості стійких організацій, які оперативнo відновлюють керованість і виконують робочі завдання. Розглянуто лідерські якості, розвиток яких є доцільним у колективі в умовах кризових змін. **Методика.** Проведений аналіз охопив наукові публікації за темою дослідження. У дослідженні використано емпіричні методи для визначення ефективності розвитку лідерських якостей серед менеджерів бібліотек. **Результати.** Розглянуто вплив стану технічної та соціальної складових на життєстійкість організації. На технічні складові складно впливати з боку адміністрації бібліотеки, на відміну від соціальних. Саме тому основна увага приділяється регулюванню соціальних складових. На основі практичних результатів роботи бібліотеки обґрунтовано доцільність формування стилю керівництва для забезпечення стійкості бібліотеки в кризових умовах. **Висновки.** Таким чином, ми вважаємо, що в умовах кризи стійкість організації може бути підвищена за рахунок розвитку лідерських якостей керівництва бібліотеки. У період невизначених кризових умов воєнного стану ці лідерські стилі нормалізують психологічний клімат у колективі та налаштовують працівників на результат.

Ключові слова: управління; академічні бібліотеки; організаційна стійкість; етичне лідерство; демократичне лідерство; трансформаційне лідерство; спільне лідерство

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